

A Comparison between Male Sprinters and Long Distance Runner within Body Composition

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to compare the body composition between male Sprinters and Long distance runner. The subjects were selected from the male Sprinters and Long distance runner of different colleges and training centers, who had participated last two years at Assam state level competitions for this study. Ten (10) male Sprinters and Long distance runners were selected as the subject for the study. Selected body composition such as Standing Height, Weight, Humerus Biepicondylar, Wrist Diameter, Femur Biepicondylar, Ankle Diameter, Upper arm Circumference, Forearm Circumference, Thigh Circumference, Calf Circumference, Bicep Skinfold, Forearm Skinfold, Suprailiac Skinfold, Subscapular Skinfold, Thigh Skinfold, Calf Skinfold were presented to compare the Sprinters and Long distance runners. To see the significant difference of selected body composition variables among the Sprinters and Long distance runners, the analysis of "mean, standard deviation and t test" was applied at .05 level of significance. The Sprinters are found to be taller and having greater diameters and circumferences and leaner in all skinfolds except suprailiac skinfold. The Long distance runners found to be heavier and having greater upper arm and forearm circumferences and leaner in suprailiac skinfold than sprinters. However, the Sprinters have greater bone mass, muscle mass and less fat percentage than Long distance Runners.

Keywords:

Body Composition, Sprinters, Long Distance Runners

1. INTRODUCTION

The scientifically proved that the body composition of two persons is never alike. It may differ in many ways like body size, structure, shape, weight, fat etc. By nature human beings are competitive and aspires from excellence in every field. Sport is not an exception, changes are the order of the day. Changes are taking place every day in every walk of life. Life of people, their philosophy, ways of living etc. are undergoing changes due to basic and applied research in various fields. New techniques are developed in laboratories and scientific methods are applied to obtain the level of performance. Sports by their very nature are enjoyable, challenging, absorbing and require a certain amount of skill and physical condition. With all round advancement in the science of sports the new disciplines are emerging with micro-specialization. The elements, of scientific basis of selection are being inducted in the procedure of selection of athletes at various levels in some of the advanced countries. The knowledge from many scientific disciplines is being used for improving criteria for the selection of talents. The physical educationists have designed test procedures for evaluating the fitness of young children. This difference influences their performance in some different sports events. The human body consists of several levels of structural organization. Considering the increasing stages of complexity, five levels of body composition can be envisioned. The human body is characterized by size, shape and its various dimensions. Body composition is used to describe the percentages

of fat, bone and muscular in human body. Body composition has become a major field of interest, for the sport scientists and proper assessment of body composition can help in profiling and counseling sports person. Body composition makes an important contribution to an individual's level of physical fitness for performance describes it as a state which characterizes the degree to which a person is able to function efficiently through these physical, mental, emotional, moral and spiritual components. So investigator tried to such hidden factors which help to increase the level of performance of Sprinters and Long Distance Runners.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Participants

Sixty (60) male subjects which were divided into two groups 30 sprinters and 30 long distance runners and both groups having equally distributed. They were ranging in age from 18.3+5.5 years old. The sample had participated last 2 years at state level competitions. The sixty (60) sprinters and long distance runners were selected from different colleges and training centers. The investigator firstly divided the sprinters and long distance runners, random sampling technique was used.

2.2. Statistical Analysis

To analysis the significant difference of selected body composition variables among the male sprinters and long distance runners, the analysis of "mean, standard deviation and 't' test was applied at .05 level of significance.

2.3. Instruments

The following instruments used for collection of data were anthropometric rod, Weighing machine, Sliding caliper, Steel tape, Skinfold caliper, Stopwatch, Measuring tape and Shot Put.

The following standardized anthropometric measurements used method for data collection were Standing Height (cms), Weight (kg), Humerus Biepicondylar (cms), Wrist Diameter (cms), Femur Biepicondylar (cms), Ankle Diameter (cms), Upper arm Circumference (cms), Forearm Circumference (cms), Thigh Circumference (cms), Calf Circumference (cms), Bicep Skinfold (mm) Forearm Skinfold (mm), Suprailiac Skinfold (mm), Subscapular Skinfold (mm), Thigh Skinfold (mm), Calf Skinfold (mm).

Body composition components i.e. bone mass and muscle mass, percentage of body fat and body density were calculated using the formula.

3. RESULTS

The results pertaining to body composition, if any, between sprinters and long distance runners were assessed using the Student's t test and the results are shown in tables-1.

The comparison of their Standing Height, Weight, Humerus Biepicondylar, Wrist Diameter, Femur Biepicondylar, Ankle Diameter, Upper arm Circumference, Forearm Circumference, Thigh Circumference, Calf Circumference, Bicep Skinfold, Forearm Skinfold, Suprailiac Skinfold, Subscapular Skinfold, Thigh Skinfold, Calf Skinfold of male Sprinters and Long distance runners were shown in table 1. The mean values of Humerus Biepicondylar, Wrist Diameter, Femur Biepicondylar, Ankle Diameter, Upper arm Circumference, Thigh Circumference, Calf Circumference, Bicep Skinfold, Bone mass and Fat percentage of Sprinters and Long distance runners were (7.01 and 5.97)cms, (5.99 and 5.54)cms, (8.64 and 8.31)cms, (6.83 and 6.51)cms, (25.53 and 26.90)cms, (48.57 and 47.27)cms, (35.10 and 33.92)cms, (9.72 and 11.23)mm, (10.28 and 8.73) and (23.71 and 30.24) respectively. In statistically term cal. t ($=6.70, 3.24, 2.40, 2.78, 2.13, 2.01, 2.03, 2.05, 4.56$ and 6.86) $>$ tab t .05 (59) ($=2.01$), H_0 (null hypothesis) is rejected at .05 level of significance.

Table 1: Mean Value (SD) of Body Composition In The Sprinters And Long Distance Runners

Dimensions	Mean		Sd		T-Value
	Sprinters	Long Distance	Sprinters	Long Distance	
Height (cms)	168.2	166.8	166.8	166.87	0.68
Body weight (Kg)	61.20	62.25	9.37	10.54	0.41
Humerus biepicondylar (cms)	7.01	5.97	0.60	0.60	6.70*
Wrist diameter (cms)	5.99	5.54	0.53	0.54	3.24*
Femer biepicondylar (cms)	8.64	8.31	0.45	0.59	2.40*
Ankle diameter (cms)	6.83	6.51	0.44	0.45	2.78*
Upper arm circumference (cms)	25.53	26.90	2.59	2.38	2.13*
Forarm circumference (cms)	24.80	25.47	2.31	1.98	1.20
Thigh circumference (cms)	48.57	47.27	1.82	3.05	2.01*
Calf circumference (cms)	35.10	33.92	1.93	2.55	2.03*
Biceps skinfold (mm)	9.72	11.23	2.31	3.32	2.05*
Forearm skinfold (mm)	7.68	8.93	2.27	3.14	1.77
Suprailiac skinfold	16.37	15.60	7.35	6.64	0.42
Subscapular skinfold (mm)	12.23	13.03	5.18	5.81	0.58
Thigh skinfold (mm)	12.13	13.03	2.86	3.00	1.19
Calf skinfold (mm)	13.53	14.57	2.49	2.19	1.38
Bone mass	10.28	8.73	1.41	1.22	4.56*
Muscle mass	25.25	24.29	3.42	3.51	1.07
Fat percentage	23.71	30.24	3.99	3.36	6.86*

The comparison of their height, body weight, forarm circumference, forarm skinfold, suprailiac skinfold, subscapular skinfold, thigh skinfold, calf skinfold and muscle mass of Sprinters and Long distance runners were (168.2 and 166.8)cms, (61.20 and 62.25)kg, (24.80 and 25.47)cms, (7.68 and 8.93)mm, (16.37 and 15.60)mm, (12.23 and 13.03)mm, (12.13 and 13.03)mm, (13.53 and 14.57)mm and (25.25 and 24.29) respectively. The calculated "t" value (=0.68, 0.41, 1.20, 1.77, 0.42, 0.58, 1.19, 1.38 and 1.07) < tab t.05 (59) (=2.01), Ho (null hypothesis) is accepted at .05 level of significance.

Result indicates that male sprinter were found to be taller than long distance runner, male long distance runner were found to be heavier than sprinters, male sprinters has greater humerus biepicondylar diameter, wrist diameter, femur biepicondylar, ankle diameter, upper arm circumference, thigh circumference, calf circumference than sprinters, leaner biceps skinfold than long distance runner, greater bone mass and lesser fat percentage than long distance runners.

It may also concluded that no significant change was noted in the height, body weight, forarm circumference, forarm skinfold, suprailiac skinfold, subscapular skinfold, thigh skinfold, calf skinfold and muscle mass. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Body Composition

Results of the present study revealed that male sprinters have taller, greater diameters, circumferences except upper-arm and fore-arm circumferences and leaner in skinfolds except suprailiac skinfold. Long distance runners have greater upper-arm and forearm circumferences and leaner in suprailiac skinfold. These findings substantiate the assertion that the several studies have shown that compared to other sports using body power, the sprinters in the present study have greater bone mass, more muscle mass and lesser fat percentage. This may be due to wider bone diameters, more developed girths; this may be an effect of strenuous training, different skills movements, genetics factors and different diet patterns as compared to long distance runners.

5. CONCLUSION

Keeping the results and discussion in view, the conclusions drawn that in comparison with long distance runners, sprinters are found to be taller and having greater diameters and circumferences. Sprinters are further found to be leaner in all skinfolds except suprailiac skinfold. Long distance runners are found to be heavier and having greater upper arm and forearm circumferences than sprinters. Long distance runners are further found to be leaner in suprailiac skinfold. Sprinters have greater bone mass, muscle mass and less fat percentage than long distance runners.

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